

A Study of Emotional Intelligence among College Students, Greater Noida

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Abstract:-

➤ Introduction

Emotional Intelligence is a vital component in both personal and professional aspects of life. Despite more than 30 years of research, there is still no concrete proof that one concept defines emotional intelligence as the capacity of an individual to recognise, evaluate, and control his or her own and other people's emotions. To measure multifaceted emotional intelligence, there are many different tools and methods. The Emotional Intelligent Quotient is another name for it. It is described as "the capacity of a person to perceive, evaluate, and manage his or her own and other people's emotions."

➤ Objectives

- To measure the level of emotional intelligence among the nursing students using the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire.
- To find the association and co-relation of emotional intelligence with selected socio-demographic variables and related traits.

➤ Methodology

The study was conducted in Sharda School of Nursing Science And Research, Sharda University. Total of 91 samples who satisfied the inclusive criteria were selected using a probability systematic random sampling technique. The baseline data was collected using demographic performa and structured questionnaire was used to assess the level of emotional intelligence among the nursing students. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data collected.

➤ Results

A total of 91 students were elected through probability systematic random sampling technique. Our study depicts that the socio- demographic variables had shown statistically significant association between four

dimensions of emotional intelligence- - wellbeing, self-control, emotionality and sociability among nursing students with chi-square value of $p < 0.05$ level. Also it was found that the demographic variables- type of family, occupation and income had shown statistically significant association with emotional intelligence among nursing students with chi-square value of $p < 0.05$ level. P value is significant in occupation of mother as 0.016, 0.040 in annual income, 0.00001** in type of family. The distribution and frequency of emotional intelligence among the nursing students shows that 46% students have high emotional intelligence.

➤ Conclusion

Present study concluded that majority of study participants have high level of emotional intelligence because of better growth and good parenting of students by housewife mothers as percentage is high 78.2% may be because of more time spent with their children. A student who belongs to low middle class family i.e. annual income of the family is less than 1 lakh has high emotional intelligence of 63.04%. Students living in nuclear family have high emotional intelligence of 52.17%.

Keywords:- Emotional Intelligence, Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire, Nursing Students

I. INTRODUCTION

"The emotional brain responds to an event more quickly than the thinking brain."

Daniel Goleman

Emotional Intelligence is a vital component in both personal and professional aspects of life. Emotional intelligence is the capacity of an individual to acknowledge, evaluate, and control his or her own and other people's emotions. The Emotional Intelligent Quotient is another name for it. ⁽¹⁾

Emotional Intelligence (otherwise known as Emotional Quotient or EQ) is the ability of the student to understand, use and manage their own emotions in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges and defuse conflict. Dealing with emotions, understanding them correctly, utilising them to think effectively, and managing those emotions while delivering great care in all areas, including physical, mental, social, and spiritual, is the fundamental foundation of nursing^(1,2).

The development of intelligence starts since the intra-uterine life of the fetus and this process continues throughout the life. The nursing profession directs that the nurse must possess emotional intelligence in order to provide patients with high-quality care. This emotional intelligence allows the nurse to improvise emotional information for specific patients and improves patient care through intentional communication and therapeutic relationships.⁽²⁾

Leadership traits, professional performance, critical thinking, coping mechanisms, soft skills, self-reflection, self-awareness, interpersonal collaboration, and many other traits have all been connected to emotional intelligence.⁽³⁾

EI significantly influences the performance of the nursing student and thus the care of the patient. This study is focused on the measurement of one or more of the following specific emotional intelligence, related traits or abilities such as –

- Well being
- Self-control
- Emotionality
- Sociability

Our capacity for motivation, empathy, reasoning, stress management, resilience, communication, and the ability to explore and navigate a variety of arguments and situations are all aided by emotional intelligence (EI), which is the intersection of intellect and emotion^(4,5).

One component of emotional intelligence is the ability to interpret complex information about one's own and other people's emotions and utilise that information as a guide for thought and behaviour. Therefore, those with high emotional intelligence pay close attention to how they use, comprehend, and control their emotions, and these abilities help them in adapting behaviour that is advantageous to both themselves and others. Emotional Intelligence consists of the capacity to interact with state-of-the-art statistics processing approximately one's personal and others' emotions.⁽⁴⁾

Emotional intelligence helps in dealing with impulsive feelings such as anger and disappointment in the nurse-patient relationships. Emotional Intelligence leads to better retention and successful completion of specific task given (similar studies are also given by Stenhouse et al., 2016). It also improves the quality of academic achievement and

enhances motivation among student nurses (this is supported by research work of Pooja Yadav and Naved Iqbal, Jamia Milia Islamia, 2013). Emotional Intelligence will help nursing students during burnout situations either in academics or clinically along with personal and professional life.

➤ Objectives of the Study

- To measure the level of emotional intelligence among the nursing students using the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire.
- To find the association and co-relation of emotional intelligence with selected socio-demographic variables and related traits.

II. RESEARCH APPROACH

For the current study, quantitative research approach has been adopted. Student's emotional intelligence is assessed through Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire.

A. Research Design

The research design used for the present study was descriptive research design.

B. Settings

The study was conducted at SSNSR, Sharda University, Greater Noida. Sharda University is a leading Educational institution based out of Greater Noida, Delhi NCR. The University is approved by UGC. Sharda School of Nursing Science & Research encompasses a full spectrum of undergraduate and graduate programmes that prepare nursing scholars for a career in the healthcare industry. With SSNSR degree, graduates enter the health care field with a solid foundation in research, theory, clinical skills, and hands-on community service, which sets them apart as leaders in their profession, who are qualified to bring change in the face of health care delivery.

C. Population

In this study, the focus is on target population of nursing students of BSc N 2nd year, 3rd year and GNM 2nd year SSNSR, Greater Noida during the period of data collection.

III. SAMPLE

The sample of the present study comprises of Nursing students of Sharda School of Nursing Science & Research, Sharda University, who were present at the time of data collection.

A. Sampling Technique

A list of students from each year is collected using attendance register and probability systematic random sampling technique is done.

B. Sample Size Calculation

Assuming the proportion of emotional intelligence among nursing students as 13.97% (Anticipated prevalence from previous study in Gujarat, 5% alpha error, 95% confidence interval, absolute precession of +/-5%, the required Sample size is 90 is calculated by using Open Epi software version3.

C. Criteria for Sample Selection

➤ Inclusion Criteria

- Students of SSNSR who were willing to participate.
- Students who are available during the study.

➤ Exclusion Criteria

- Nursing students who has already attended emotional intelligence training program.
- Students undergoing any other counseling session.

IV. DEVELOPMENT OF DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

Data collection instrument includes Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (developed by K.V.Petrides) the family of TEIQue instruments is available, free of charge, for academic and clinical research, with a wide range of materials also available for commercial purposes.

A. Description of the Data Collection Instrument

The data collection instrument consists of 2 parts namely Socio-demographic variables, and questions related to emotional intelligence.

➤ Section A:

• Demographic Information

This section deals with socio-demographic variables. It includes variables such as age, gender, educational status of father and mother, occupation of father and mother, annual family income, residence / domicile, type of family, religion, extra-curricular activities.

➤ Section B

• TEIQue- Form

This 30-item form includes two items from each of the 15 facets of the TEIQue. Items were selected primarily on the basis of their correlations with the corresponding total facet scores, which ensured broad coverage of the sampling domain of the construct. The TEIQue rated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“Strongly disagree”) to 7 (“Strongly agree”). It yields scores on 15 facets, 4 factors, and global trait EI.

B. Scoring and Interpretation

A self-administered questionnaire (SAQ) was used to collect data from the participants, which had 2 sections: section A had demographic characteristics like age, gender, place of living. Section B was the valid and reliable “Trait emotional intelligence questionnaire–short forms (TEIQue-

SF)” developed by Petrides et al which composed of 30 items designed to assess global emotional intelligence traits. TEIQue-SF scale has four dimensions: well-being, self-control, emotionality, and sociability. It is a Likert scale ranging from 1 (completely disagree) to 7 (completely agree). Reversing was done for negative scoring items. Higher total scores indicated higher EI levels. TEIQue-SF is a valid and reliable tool with the Cronbach’s alpha of 0.86.8. The Cronbach’s alpha in our study participants was 0.802 indicating high reliability and validity.

The EI mean scores of nursing students are classified as low, normal, and good EI. The low EI scores varied between 1 and 3, normal scores varied between 4 and 5, and good EI score between 6 and 7 (proportion of emotional intelligence among four dimensions). The low score ranged <111, medium score ranged between 111-137 and high ranged >137 (proportion of emotional intelligence among students).

C. Ethical Consideration

Prior permission was obtained from the Head of the Sharda school of Nursing Science institution. Written informed consent was obtained from the participants before they were enrolled in the study.

D. Data Collection Procedure

The data collection was carried out after obtaining necessary institution approval. An informed consent was obtained from participants after which, the questionnaire were distributed. The data was collected within 3 days using a questionnaire which includes demographic information and questionnaire related to emotional intelligence. Students who follow the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study.

E. Plan For Data Analysis

- Data were entered into Microsoft excel sheet and analysed using SPSS.
- Categorical variables like gender, education, monthly income, residence, religion were summarized as proportions with 95% confidence interval.
- Continuous variable age is described by mean with standard deviation with 95% confidence interval.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

An analysis is a method of formulating data in a way that the research questions can be answered. The collected data was organised, analysed, interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. A total of 91 study participants were enrolled for the study. Results of the study will be discussed under following headings –

- Section 1- Socio Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants.
- Section 2- Proportion of Emotional Intelligence among Students.
- Section 3- Proportion of Emotional Intelligence among Four Dimensions- Wellbeing, Self-Control, Emotionality and Sociability.

- Section 4 - Association of Socio Demographic and Emotional Intelligence of the Study Participants
- Section 5 – Co-Relation of Socio Demographic and Emotional Intelligence among Four Dimensions- Wellbeing, Self-Control, Emotionality and Sociability.

- Section 1-Socio Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

Table 1 Distribution of Socio Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants.

Variables	Category	Frequency	(%)
AGE	18 -20	39	42.9
	20-22	49	53.8
	22-24	3	3.3
	24 and above	0	0
GENDER	Male	34	37.4
	Female	57	62.6
EDUCATION OF FATHER	Primary	9	9.9
	Secondary	20	22.0
	Graduate	48	52.7
	Post Graduate	13	14.3
	Doctorate	1	1.1
EDUCATION OF MOTHER	Primary	15	16.5
	Secondary	34	37.4
	Graduate	28	30.8
	Post Graduate	12	13.2
	Doctorate	2	2.2
OCCUPATION OF FATHER	Farmer	9	9.8
	Private Job	32	35.16
	Government Job	24	26.37
	Business	26	28.57
OCCUPATION OF MOTHER	Housewife	71	78.0
	Private job	6	6.6
	Government Job	13	14.3
	Business	1	1.1
ANNUAL FAMILY INCOME	Below 1 Lakh	55	60.4
	1-5 Lakh	23	25.3
	5-10 Lakh	5	5.5
	10-15 Lakh	3	3.3
	15 and above	5	5.5
RESIDENCE/DOMICILE	Urban	67	73.6
	Rural	24	26.4
TYPE OF FAMILY	Joint(5-6 members)	33	36.3
	Nuclear(2-3 members)	46	50.5
	Extended(more than 7 members)	12	13.2
RELIGION	Hinduism	75	82.4
	Muslim	3	3.3
	Sikhism	1	1.1
	Christian	12	13.2
	Others	0	0
EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES	Sports/Games	35	38.46
	Music/Dance	30	32.96
	Arts/Literature	12	13.18
	Others	14	15.38

Among the total 91 study participants mean age of the students was 20.21 and standard deviation was 21.71

The **TABLE 1** shows frequency and percentage distribution of socio-demographic variables among the nursing students. **Highest percentage** is 53.8% in age group of 20-22 years, 62.6% in gender female, 52.7% in education of father as graduate, 37.4% in secondary education of mother, 35.16% in private job of father, 78% in mother’s as housewife, 60.4% in below 1 lakh annual income, 50.5% belongs to nuclear family.

➤ Section 2- Proportion of Emotional Intelligence among Students.

Table 2 Distribution of Emotional Intelligence of the Study Participants.

VARIABLES	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (%)
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE	LOW(<111)	8
	MEDIUM(111-137)	37
	HIGH(>137)	46

Fig1 Bar Diagram Showing Level of EI

The **TABLE 2** shows the distribution and frequency of emotional intelligence among the nursing students. 46% students have high emotional intelligence.

➤ Section 3- Proportion of Emotional Intelligence among Four Dimensions- Wellbeing, Self-Control, Emotionality and Sociability.

Table 3 Distribution of Emotional Intelligence of Study Participants among Four Dimensions- Wellbeing, Self-Control, Emotionality and Sociability.

VARIABLES	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (%)
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE	LOW (1-3)	18 (19.78%)
	MEDIUM (4-5)	73 (80.21%)
	HIGH	0

Fig 2 Bar Diagram Showing Level of EI among Four Dimensions

The **TABLE 3** shows distribution of emotional intelligence among four dimensions- Well-being, sociability, self-control and emotionality.80.21% students have medium level of emotional intelligence.

➤ *Section 4 - Association of Socio Demographic Variables and Emotional Intelligence of the Study Participants.*

Table 4 Association between of Socio Demographic Variables and Emotional Intelligence among Nursing Students.

Variables	Category	Low		Medium		High		Chi – square x2	df	P value
		n	%	n	%	n	%			
AGE	18 -20	3	37.5	11	29.72	25	54.34	5.761	4	0.218
	20-22	5	62.5	24	64.86	20	43.47			
	22-24	0	0	2	5.40	1	2.17			
GENDER	Male	1	12.5	15	40.54	18	39.13	2.334	2	0.311
	Female	7	87.5	22	59.45	28	60.83			
EDUCATION OF FATHER	Primary	0	0	2	5.40	7	15.21	5.650	8	0.686
	Secondary	1	12.5	10	27.02	9	19.56			
	Graduate	5	62.5	20	54.05	23	50.00			
	Post Graduate	2	25	5	13.51	6	13.04			
	Doctorate	0	0	0	0	1	2.17			
EDUCATION OF MOTHER	Primary	1	12.5	6	16.21	8	17.39	7.157	8	0.520
	Secondary	2	25.0	19	51.35	13	28.26			
	Graduate	4	50.0	8	21.62	16	34.78			
	Post Graduate	1	12.5	3	8.10	8	17.39			
	Doctorate	0	0	1	2.70	1	2.17			
OCCUPATION OF FATHER	Farmer	0	0	4	10.81	5	10.86	4.98	6	0.289
	Private Job	2	25	13	35.13	17	7.82			
	Government Job	4	50	11	29.72	8	17.39			
	Business	2	25	9	24.32	16	34.78			
OCCUPATION OF MOTHER	Housewife	4	50	31	83.78	36	78.26	15.614	6	0.016*
	Private job	3	37.5	2	5.40	1	2.17			
	Government Job	1	12.5	4	10.81	8	17.39			
	Business	0	0	0	0	1	2.17			
ANNUAL FAMILY INCOME	Below 1 Lakh	4	50	22	59.45	29	63.04	16.206	8	0.040*
	1-5 Lakh	1	12.5	11	29.72	11	23.31			
	5-10 Lakh	0	0	3	8.10	2	4.34			
	10-15 Lakh	2	25	0	0	1	2.17			
	15 and above	1	12.5	1	2.70	3	6.52			
RESIDENCE/DOMICILE	Urban	7	87.5	26	70.27	34	73.91	1.010	2	0.604
	Rural	1	12.5	11	29.72	12	26.08			
TYPE OF FAMILY	Joint(5-6 members)	0	0	15	40.54	18	39.13	29.921	4	0.00001*
	Nuclear(2-3 members)	2	25	20	54.05	24	52.17			
	Extended(more than 7 members)	6	75	2	5.40	4	8.69			
RELIGION	Hinduism	6	75	29	78.37	40	86.95	15.002	6	0.20
	Muslim	0	0	3	8.10	0	0			
	Sikhism	1	12.5	0	0	0	0			
	Christian	1	12.5	5	13.51	6	13.04			
EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES	Sports/Games	2	25	13	35.13	20	43.47	3.8296	6	0.429
	Music/Dance	4	50	10	27.02	16	34.78			
	Arts/Literature	0	0	8	21.62	4	8.69			
	Others	2	25	6	16.21	6	13.04			

The **TABLE 4** depicts that the demographic variables- **type of family, occupation and income** had shown statistically significant association with emotional intelligence among nursing students with chi-square value of **p<0.05 level**. P value is significant in occupation of mother as 0.016, 0.040 in annual income, 0.00001 in type of family.

➤ *Section 5 – Co-Relation of Socio Demographic Variables and Emotional Intelligence among Four Dimensions- Wellbeing, Self-Control, Emotionality and Sociability.*

Table 5 Co-Relation of Emotional Intelligence and Traits - Wellbeing, Self-Control, Emotionality and Sociability.

Traits	Cronbach's Alpha value
Well Being	0.37
SelfControl	0.18
Emotionality	0.33
Sociability	0.31
Total Alpha	0.66

The table 5 shows significant association between emotional intelligence and traits with alpha value of greater than 0.50.

VI. DISCUSSION

A total of 91 students were elected through probability systematic random sampling technique. Our study depicts that the socio- demographic variables had shown statistically not significant association between four dimensions of emotional intelligence- - wellbeing, self-control, emotionality and sociability among nursing students with chi-square value of **p<0.05 level**. Also it was found that the demographic variables- **type of family, occupation and income** had shown statistically significant association with emotional intelligence among nursing students with chi-square value of **p<0.05 level**. P value is significant in occupation of mother as 0.016, 0.040 in annual income, 0.00001 in type of family. The distribution and frequency of emotional intelligence among the nursing students shows that 46% students have high emotional intelligence. The results are similar to study conducted by Mr. Thamizhselvan, K and Mrs. Vembu, K study have shown that level of emotional intelligence is average (62.8%) among nursing students⁷. In relation to study done by Binal Joshi the result shows students have average 130 sample (72.63%), good 25 (13.97%), poor 24 (13.41%).

VII. CONCLUSION

Present study concluded that maturity of study participants have high level of emotional intelligence because of better growth and good parenting of students by housewife mothers as percentage is high 78.2% may be because of more time spent with their children. A student who belongs to low middle class family that is annual family income has high emotional intelligence of 63.04%. Students living in nuclear family have high emotional intelligence of 52.17%.

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